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Tidal energy assessment using a nested numerical hydrodynamics model

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Abstract

A numerical hydrodynamics model for the Great Bay Estuary, New Hampshire, within the Gulf of Maine was developed and applied to assess tidal marine hydrokinetic energy resources. The model has realistic forcing that includes tides, subtidal currents, atmospheric forcing, and river discharges, and is verified by comparing with observations. To accurately assess the available tidal energy resource, long three-dimensional model simulations of greater than 30 days are produced, with time series of tri-directional currents saved at 1 second intervals at selected locations corresponding to a cross-river transect and where other instruments were deployed in situ. The spatial resolution of the model is refined by offline nesting approaches, and differences in velocity distributions are examined as a function of spatial model horizontal resolution ranging ~5-30 m. Estuarine currents are hindcast and their available renewable energy is assessed around the Atlantic Marine Energy Center (AMEC) Tidal Energy Test Site located at the Memorial Bridge in the Piscataqua River between New Hampshire and Maine. Current speeds along the cross-river transect near the site are used to estimate the ebb and flood current probability density functions and assess the tidal marine renewable resource. Dependence on temporal sampling and averaging intervals will be investigated. Simulations from the model will be compared to observations obtained from bottom-mounted, upward-looking acoustic doppler current profilers. The usefulness of high-resolution hydrodynamic models to predict available tidal energy resources will be discussed for the AMEC-UNH Tidal Energy Test Site. The high-resolution hydrodynamic model will then be used to provide detailed spatiotemporal inflow conditions for engineering CFD models, which have much greater resolution requirements at the device or farm scale.

Keywords: hydrodynamics model; tidal energy assessment; CFD

1. Great Bay Modeling System

A hydrodynamics circulation model for the Great Bay was developed using the Regional Ocean Modeling System (ROMS)^[1]. Spatial resolution of the model grid is about 30 m but can be increased by nested grid. The model resolves realistic forcing: tides, subtidal currents, wind, atmospheric pressure, surface heating, cooling, precipitation, evaporation, and river discharge. Tidal and subtidal components are obtained by the Oregon State University TPXO9 tide model^[2] and the Gulf of Maine Operational Forecast System (GOMOFS)^[3], respectively. Surface boundary conditions (atmospheric forcings) are obtained by European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)

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ERA5 reanalysis dataset^[4]. Major rivers that discharge into the Great Bay Estuary system (Salmon Falls, Cocheco, Bellamy, Oyster, Lamprey, Squamscott, Winnicut) are considered in the model and the river discharge is based on the observations provided by United States Geological Survey (USGS). Fig. 1 shows model domain, bathymetry, and location of rivers.

The model is verified by comparing *in situ* observations and shows reasonable performance (Fig. 2). Sea surface height and velocities, where tidal components are predominant in the Great Bay^[5], are comparable with the observations, so we expect that the model can be used for tidal energy resource assessment. Results will be presented at the UMERC conference.

Fig. 1. Model domain, bathymetry, and location of rivers (red circles).

Fig. 2. Model-data comparison for sea surface height from June 2022 to February 2023.

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